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Sale and Sale Promotion

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ABSTRACT

Consumer behavior is a set of behavioral characteristics and activities that they take when buying products and services that they use for their needs. Consumer activities include informing, evaluating substitutes and brands, and the buying act itself. Given fair market performance and free competition, it is important for the consumer to know what product or service he can do best to satisfy needs or wants. In this way, it is necessary to make a qualitative decision based on the evaluation of the value of the product or service purchased and the post-consumer satisfaction analysis.

In order to help explain customer behavior more easily, it is necessary to know the marketing and sales methods, the process by which certain actions of the company's tools and activities create and make an offer. For businesses, marketing is important for reasons that include a market analysis that also implies an analysis of consumer behavior. Today, as globalization is increasingly strong, consumer behavior is important not only for a better understanding of their characteristics, but also for easier market segmentation and easier placement. products or services in the target market. To ensure a secure income, companies need to constantly monitor the dynamics of consumer behavior - so it is necessary to analyze the market before developing the product, when developing in the testing phase, analyze the behavior when consuming the product, when placing a product in market, constantly monitoring and comparing consumer behavior in the market, adapting to the product and finally assessing customer satisfaction by using customer feedback and returning it for another purchase which is of particular importance for the realization of this ways of selling and promoting it.

SALE PROMOTION

Like everything else about business, sales methods change on a regular basis. The way we sell and reach out to customers will of course reflect changes in our methods of communication and applied technology.

The process should begin with a clear target audience in mind: potential company product buyers, current users, decision makers or influencers, individuals, groups, particular audiences or the general public. Target audiences are an important influence on communications decisions on what to say, how to say, when to say it, where to say it, and to whom to say it is often important to define the target audience in terms of usage and loyalty. Is it simply a target audience loyal to the brand or competing brand or is it simply one that moves from one brand to another. If the target audience is a user, is the user larger or smaller? Communication strategies will vary depending on the use and loyalty involved. and the strategy used in terms of using and promoting sales techniques. The term "promotion" is usually an internally used expression by a marketing company, but not normally in the public or market - phrases like "special offer" are more common. Promotion is one of the elements of market mix and a term often used in marketing. It is the specification of the five promotional or promotional plans. These elements are personal sales, advertising, sales promotion, direct mail marketing and publicity. A promotional mix determines how much attention should be paid to each of the five categories, and how much budget money for each.

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Definition of sales promotion

Sales promotion includes promotional and interest-generating activities that are usually short-term marketing events, in addition to advertising, personal selling, publicity and direct marketing. The purpose of sales promotion is to stimulate, motivate and influence the acquisition and other desired behavioral responses of the company's customers.

Haugh (1983) stated that sales promotion is a direct incentive that provides an added value or incentive for the product to the sales force, distributor, or end consumer with the primary objective of creating an immediate sale. Modern marketing leader Philip Kotler noted that sales promotions that mostly last for the short term consisted of a diverse array of incentives that were used to motivate consumers to make large amounts of purchases, some of which could be judgments, on the product predetermined and rapidly. There are many definitions of sales promotion tools, but they all have one common ultimate goal of directly driving consumers to buy in order to increase instant sales volume.

Sales promotion story

When tracing the origins of sales promotion tools in the modern retail sector, all the traces point us to the mid-19th century. In 1853, a hat shop in America held a promotional activity, in which every customer who bought a particular brand of hat was offered a photo service for free. While the camera was not a common thing at the time, customers felt proud when they were shown the picture of wearing a hat. Therefore, the event eventually attracted many customers and even people who lived far away came to the store and bought hats of that brand because of the photography. The store, on the other hand, became famous after its successful hat-brand promotion and customer photography activity. Later, different types of sales promotion tools were introduced into the retail market.

In the 1980s, the amount of budget used in sales promotion was similar to that used in advertising. Sales promotion costs have increased over the next 20-30 years and the amount of growth was phenomenal. By the end of the 20th century, according to Cox Direct's Annual Promotional Practices Survey, many companies spent about three-quarters of their total promotional budget on sales promotion, with the quarter remaining in advertising. Retailers say advertising offers a reason for shopping, while sales promotion tools simulate shopping. So they want to apply sales promotion tools to target customers for a fast sales promoter and they want immediate results.

Sales promotion features

Writing about sales promotion tools, Prof. Philip Kotler notes 3 distinctive features.

- Communication: They receive attention and usually provide information that can lead the consumer to the product.
- Incentives: They include some concessions, incentives or contributions that give value to the consumer.
- Invitation: They include a special invitation to engage in the transaction.

Sales promotion offers a direct incentive to act by providing extra value over and above what is built into the product at its normal price. These temporary incentives are usually provided at a time and place where the purchase decision is made. Not only are sales promotions very common under current competitive market conditions, they are growing at a rapid pace.

These promotions are direct incentives. Despite acting directly, sales promotions are quite complicated and are also a rich marketing tool with innumerable creative opportunities created by the imagination of promotion planners. Sales promotion is often referred to by various names such as "additional purchase value". Today many companies in almost all sectors offer some kind of promotion scheme. These sectors range from automotive to beverages, from financial services to food, from household items to services, from household products to business products, from personal care to textiles and clothing.

Sales Promotion Tool Categories

Philip Kotler mentioned thirteen sales promotion tools which included:

- Sample
- Vouchers

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- Discounts
 - price packages
 - Premium
 - frequency programs
 - rewards
 - patronage awards
 - free trials
 - Product guarantees
 - link in promotion
 - Cross-promotion
 - Display and demonstration of points of purchase

In recent years, new sales promotion tools have emerged in the market as well as new distribution platforms, such as patronage pricing from credit cards and e-coupons through interactive electronic devices via email, mobile telephony and Point-Of-Sale (POS). Currently, the main sales promotion tools offered by various retail sectors in Hong Kong and Beijing are shown as follows:

- Direct price / discount
- Price discount is a temporary reduction in the listed product price.
- Coupon (including printed coupon, electronic coupon)
- Printed coupons, available in magazines and newspapers or at the point of purchase, or electronic / mobile coupon, which can be downloaded from the Internet either via email or via SMS, entitle the consumer to a discount price for some products.
- Bon Bonus / discount package for one package
- Provide extra quantities of regular priced product in an expanded package or offer a special product package at a discounted price.
- Buy-one-get-one for free
- Another item is offered for free if the customer purchases an item of a regular priced product. "Buy-two-one-free" and buy - "three-get-one-free" are similar offers under the same placement justification.
- Special premium / gift / advertising
- Free gift / item offered in exchange for purchasing one or more products.
- Joint promotion / linking
- Another product is offered for free or at a discount after purchasing a particular product.
- Est Dispute, game
- Lucky games, activities, competitions and retreats are offered after purchasing a particular product or reaching a certain amount of value.
- Membership program
- Free product discounts or rewards offered upon joining the membership program; members are later entitled to certain privileges (such as additional discounts or priority services, etc.).
- Free sample
- Provides consumers with a small portion of a product, usually new to the market, for trial.

Some scholars have attempted to classify sales promotion tools into several categories. Dommermuth (1989) suggested two types of sales promotion categories by types of incentives. One was from economic incentives, including discount, coupon and value, while another was from psychological incentives, including premium and joint promotion. Shimp (1990) categorized sales promotion tools based on the time provided by sales

incentives, immediate and deferred sales promotion tools. Discount, premium and bonus packages were grouped as instant sales promotion tools, while coupons, raffles and discounts were grouped as promotional sales promotion tools. Campbell and Diamond (1990) grouped two types of sales promotion, monetary sales promotion and non-monetary sales promotion.

Discounts and discounts are examples of incentives to promote monetary sales that allow the impact of the reference price. Premium and judgment offers are examples of incentives to promote non-monetary sales, which are considered an additional benefit and are unable to influence the reference price.

Purpose of sales promotion tools

In general, the goals of retailers in deploying various sales promotion tools are as follows:

stimulate clients? the desire for immediate purchase;

- generate short-term sales growth in a given product;
- increasing customer flow;
- promoting redemptions;
- to stimulate consumers' desire to try new product;
- attract new customers and encourage brand switching;
- increase retailers competition and secure market participation;
- maintain and reward existing loyal customers,
- Promotes sellers / brands, name and reputation;
- reinforce image retailers / brands; and
- comply with corporate plans through temporary incentives.

Discounting has been well documented to be an effective sales promotion tool for increasing instant sales volume. Bonus packages (Ong, 1999), specialty advertising (Lee, 2002), and continuity programs (Ong, 1999) are treated as useful tools to encourage large or repeated purchases. In addition, sampling and court offers, coupons and discounts motivate consumers to buy new products.

Sales promotion acts as a competitive tool which offers consumers an additional incentive to buy one brand over others at a retailer relative to others. Now, sales promotion has become an integral part of many retailers' marketing strategies, and the successful deployment and implementation of timely sales promotion tactics can lead to substantial increases in sales transactions and sales revenue.

Sales promotion involves some communication activities that try to provide additional value or incentives to consumers, wholesalers, retailers or other organizational customers to stimulate instant sales. These efforts may attempt to stimulate product interest, judgment, or purchase. Examples of equipment used in sales promotion include coupons, samples, premiums, points of purchase (POPs), contests, discounts and sweepstakes.

A promotional plan can have a wide range of objectives, including: increasing sales, accepting new products, creating brand equity, positioning, competing retaliation or creating a corporate image. Sales promotions are another way to advertise. Sales promotions are twofold because they are used to gather information about what kind of customers you are attracted to, and where they are, and to begin sales. Promoters use online advertising, special events, support and newsletters to advertise their product. Many times buying a product is an incentive like discounts, free items, or a race. This is to increase sales of a particular product. Sales promotion stands for all other forms of promotion done by the marketing employee to encourage consumers to buy their products or services. It is a communication tool that adds value to a product or service in order to encourage people to buy now, rather than at some point in the future. Sales promotion is about providing additional value to customers in order to promote an immediate sale.

Sales promotion is defined as the demand for incentive devices designed to complement advertising and facilitate personal selling. Sales promotions include things like contests and games, sweepstakes, product gifts, samples, coupons, loyalty programs and discounts. The ultimate goal of sales promotions is to stimulate

potential customers to action. There are different ways to promote a product in different media areas.

In essence, however, there are three basic objectives of promotion. These are:

- To present information to consumers as well as others.
- To increase demand.
- To distinguish a product.

Sales promotions can be directed either to the customer, sales staff or members of the distribution channel (such as retailers). Sales promotions that target the consumer are called consumer sales promotions. Targeted sales promotions at retailers and wholesalers are called trade sales promotions. Some sales promotions, especially those with unusual methods, are considered fraudulent by many.

Sales Promotional Techniques

Price deal: A temporary reduction in price, such as 50%.

Loj Loyalty Rewards Program: Customers collect points or credits for purchases and redeem them for rewards.

- Cents-off deal: Offers a brand at a lower price. Price reduction can be a percentage listed on the packaging.
- Packaging Package: Packaging offers the consumer a certain percentage of the product for the same price (for example, an additional 25 percent).
- Coupons: Coupons have become a standard sales promotion mechanism.
- I Loss leader: the price of a popular product is temporarily reduced in order to stimulate other profitable sales.
- Free Input (FSI): A coupon is inserted in the local newspaper.
- Shelf Coupon: Coupons are present on the shelf where the product is available.
- On-line couponing: Coupons are available online. Customers crush them and take them to the store.
- Mobile Coupon: Coupons are available on a mobile phone. Customers show the offer on a cell phone to a salesperson for redemption.
- Online Interactive online promotional game: Customers play an interactive game related to the promoted product.
- Refunds: Customers are offered money back if they own the manufacturer's barcode.

CONCLUSION

In the face of ever-increasing competition in the market, the impact of globalization on business development, and at the same time on advertising development, the struggle for survival in the market and the realization of the main goal, profit is increasingly complicated. In the contemporary economy, successful is called the enterprise that receives demand for the products and services they provide.

Market orientation is an ongoing process that has the starting point for collecting market information, interpreting it in enterprise mechanisms, and providing answers based on the analysis data. The process of creating, disseminating information across the company and its response to the information gathered involves all departments and all employees from managers to lower levels. In fact, the whole process is directed at creating greater value for consumers. Thus we have come to the conclusion that at the heart of a business-oriented enterprise is the consumer and the fulfillment of his needs and desires.

The purpose of the research is to analyze the importance of different marketing activities through customer orientation through the promotion process. The results are based on a rather small sample, so the conclusions are only preliminary and instead of guidelines for further research.

Investigating a fairly general character of the overall sophistication of management in a company and its relationship to marketing activities may be a good direction for future research.

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